

The Influence of Digital Marketing, Product Variety and Product Quality on the Interest in Buying Skincare Products on the Tiktok Application

Vania Mutiara Ramadhani¹, Ahmad Mardalis²

Muhammadiyah University of Surakarta, Indonesia

Abstract: *This study aims to examine the influence of digital marketing product variety and product quality on the interest in buying skincare products on the tiktok application. The population in this study was tiktok application users. Samples were selected using purposive sampling technique, so the amount of data used is 200 data. Data collection techniques through questionnaires using google Forms. The results of the analysis in this study indicate that digital marketing has a significant effect on buying interest (H1); variety of products has a significant effect on buying interest (H2); product quality influence significant on buying interest (H3)*

Keywords: Digital Marketing, Product Variety, Product Quality, Buying Interest

I. INTRODUCTION

Media has evolved through many generations and eras. With the growth of the Internet, online social networking has become an important communication channel and also virtual communities are emerging. Social Media with an important role as a form of digital communication and entertainment, as a form of great opportunities in a business activity, especially in the process of Product Marketing. The influence of the digital world in product marketing is considered the most effective through social media because it can build relationships and increase consumer attraction through the content and reviews offered so that it can reach consumers in a wide scope.

The development of technology that began to penetrate into all fields is a challenge for the actors in the field. One of them is the field of digital marketing, where businesses are now switching markets from direct marketing media (offline) to online. Online marketing referred to here is a sale made using third-party sales applications, or more commonly called e-commerce applications. The main trigger for digital marketing is growing rapidly today, one of which is due to the Covid 19 pandemic which limits the scope of the community due to the holding of large-scale social restriction rules (PSBB) which force people not to leave their homes and carry out all forms of activities remotely (social distance). And the application that is currently a conversation among the general public is Tiktok Shop which is one of the new features developed by the Tiktok application.

The TikTok application was introduced in 2016, this application boomed in 2020 when the Covid 19 pandemic came TikTok application became an application that was downloaded a lot with the "Non- Game application" category. monthly active users of the TikTok application are 99.1 million people in Indonesia, which is the second largest number after the United States. Many categories of video content exist in the TikTok application, one of the most watched categories of video content beauty/beauty. So that the business actors of the skincare product industry utilize the TikTok application to do marketing.

TikTok is one of the applications that plays an important role in paid promotional media, which of course is directly related to digital marketing carried out by business people in the field of e-commerce. with the Tiktok application that provides the Tiktok Store feature, where the feature can be used as one of the e-commerce tools that many consumers

are interested in shopping online. Although in terms of launching Tiktok Shop, it is still not widely known by Tiktok application users.

Product quality is very important for the company to create a quality product and become the main criterion in choosing the products offered by the company. The company must maintain and improve product quality to meet the wishes of consumers with quality products the company can compete with competitors in mastering the market.

Buying interest according to Kotler & Keller (2009) buying interest is a consumer behavior that arises in response to an object that indicates the customer's desire to make a purchase. This form of promotion is an attempt to attract consumers to buy products that are marketed. When there is a product on offer, there is an attractive advertisement that is where the consumer's buying interest in the product appears.

Beauty products until now production has been increasing and can be seen as a gold mine for this particular market. Using beauty products means that customers are psychologically aware of their condition and maintain their health, cleanliness and beauty. The women's beauty care industry has been growing for a long time but the men's care market is a new emerging market. Today men are more aware of their appearance and the demand for new beauty products specifically made for men's skin that would be far behind the opinion of the older generation about "only sanitation". Although men have been buying more skin care products to take care of themselves, it is estimated that the influence to buy these products up to about 80 percent is carried by his wife or partner. Therefore, it is important to know the impact of various factors in decision making when buying skin care products. This can be understood by comparing and contrasting the men's cosmetics market and the women's cosmetics market. They have different characteristics and therefore the company must study in depth the different marketing strategies so that it is more responsive to the opening of new business opportunities as well as adding dynamics in the existing situation.

II. HEADINGS

2.1 Digital Marketing

Digital marketing is a form of direct or indirect marketing that aims to reach buyers by introducing trade products or services through social media. The use of social media can market its products on a scheduled basis, continuously to introduce its products to potential buyers.

Digital marketing continues to increase according to progress tech when in 2014 the number of ads installed on the internet has beaten television. Consumers can connect with their chosen brand on social media quickly, compared to having to shop in conventional stores.

2.2 Buying Interest

Buying interest is the attitude of consumers who appear to know and get the goods against the product that results in the desire to buy and have. The emergence of buying interest behavior due to the evaluation process of a particular brand. Kotler (2001) describes the Aida model includes:

- (1) attention. relationship between consumers and products
- (2) interest. Consumer interest in the product
- (3) desire. The consumer's desire to own the product.
- (4) action. Consumer action to decide to buy a product.

Some indicators that identify buying interest according to Ferdinand (2011) are as follows:

1. Transactional interest, re-purchase products that have been in use
2. Referential interest, recommending products to others
3. Preferential interest, an interest that describes the existence of a consumer trait that has a primary preference for the product. however, this preference can be changed if there is a problem of preference.
4. Explorative interest, the attitude of consumers wan't to know about the product to be purchased by looking for information about the product.

2.3 Variety of Products

Product diversity is a collection of all products and goods that manufacturers offer to consumers. The more the type and number of products on offer then consumers will feel satisfied (Kotler 2007:15). A product consists of tangible or intangible objects, including brand, price, color, packaging, and product quality. Including services from consumers.

Products offered can be in the form of goods and services. consumers don't just buy a product, they buy satisfaction. to facilitate the course of production, companies must maintain product confidence to consumers.

Classify products into several groups as follows:

(1) on the basis of its existence

There are two groups of the first is the goods in physical form that can be seen, felt, touched, moved. The second service, is the benefits, activities, and satisfaction that are sold for example beauty salons and lodging.

2) based on durability

Can be grouped into 2 namely non-durable goods (nondurable goods). This item is usually consumed in one or several uses. Examples of non-durable goods are food and drinks. The second is durable goods. Tangible goods that can be used many times (age for normal use is one year more). For examples clothing, electronics and others (Kotler, Philip, 2020)

Products can also be classified based on the consumer and what the product is consumed for. Products are classified into:

1) Consumer Goods

Goods consumed for the benefit of individuals or groups are consumer goods and not for business purposes. Consumer goods there are 4 types:

a) Convenience Goods are goods that are often bought and needed quickly and require minimal effort to buy and compare.

b) Shopping Goods, goods whose selection and purchase takes time or alternatives are available. The comparison includes the price, quality and model of each product. For example, skincare and cosmetics.

c) specialty Goods goods that have a unique character and identification to attract consumers, so that consumers require effort to buy them. Generally, this product is classified as luxury with brands and models that are not on the market, such as bags.

d) Unsought Goods, goods that consumers are not necessarily interested in buying even though consumers already know the existence of the product. For example: tombstones.

2) Industrial Goods

Industrial goods are goods that are consumed for business or personal needs. Industrial goods are usually processed back into other goods that are worth selling or for resale without processing them. Industrial goods there are 3 groups, namely: 1). Material and parts, goods that fully enter into the finished product. this group is divided into 2 types, namely agricultural products, animal products, and natural wealth products (fruits, vegetables, milk, oil, fish). The 2 finished material products, divided into component materials for example: yarn, cement, wire. And component parts such as motors and tires. Component Material usually still need to be processed again for example yarn in weaving into fabric. 2). Capital Items, are durable goods that are easy to develop or manage finished products. capital items are installations that include buildings and additional equipment such as typewriters and desks. This item helps the production process and does not become part of the finished product. 3). Supplies and Service, is a non-durable goods and services that provide convenience in the production process.

2. 4 Product Quality

According to Kotler and Keller(2016 :37) product quality is the ability of the product to perform its function. These capabilities include durability, reliability, accuracy, which is owned by the product as a whole. Companies must improve the quality of products or services because with the improvement of product quality can make customers feel satisfied with the products or services provided and will affect the re-purchase of the product to the customer.

In order to achieve the desired product quality, it requires a standardization of quality. The goal is to keep the products produced can meet the standards that have been set so that consumers will not lose confidence in the products purchased. Therefore, business players must be able to create products that suit the needs and tastes of consumers.

2.5 Research Framework and Hypothesis Development

H1: Digital Marketing has a positive effect on buying interest

Digital marketing by manufacturers today will make their products more quickly known by consumers so that consumer buying interest grows faster. According to Romadlon et al., (2020), Werry, (2020), and Pangkey et al., (2019), positively and significantly, digital marketing can help increase consumer buying interest.

H2: variety of products has a positive effect on buying interest

Kotler & Keller (2012) state that product variety is the sum of all the products and goods that the seller offers to the buyer. Bhatnagar & Sham, (2014) argue that the more variety of products owned, the more likely it is to meet the needs of buyers, and buyers prefer online stores with a large variety of products. Because it can increase buyer satisfaction and purchase motivation Park & Kim, (2003). The more variety of products in a market, the more likely they are to buy back the product Alvian & Prabawani, (2020). A study by Desara & Hidayat, (2021) and Wan et al., (2016) also argues that product variety has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention. According to a survey by Rainy & Widayanto, (2020), the greater the variety of products, the greater the influence on consumers' intentions to buy again. On the other hand, the limited availability of goods reduces consumer interest in buying Alvian & Prabawani, (2020).

H3: product quality has a positive effect on buying interest

Kotler and Armstrong (2012: 283) stated that product quality is related to the expertise of a product in carrying out its functions, including the totality of products, reliability, accuracy, ease of operation and repair, and other valuable attributes. According to Gaol et.al (2016: 127) posits that product quality is the expertise of a product to fulfill its functions. Liao (2018) which shows the quality of the product, as well as the price influence on consumer buying interest. With the improvement of product quality and keep innovating, consumers can be interested in buying products in accordance with what they expect, so that product quality factors can affect consumer buying interest Annafik (2012)and Meiliani (2015)

III. INDENTATIONS AND EQUATIONS

3.1 population, sample, and sampling methods

This research uses quantitative methods, quantitative research is a process of finding knowledge that uses data in the form of numbers as a tool to analyze information about what you want to know. From the perspective of its objectives, quantitative research has several points. Among them aims to develop mathematical models, where this research is not only using theory, but also important to build hypotheses related to natural phenomena that will be examined.

This study uses primary data, namely data obtained from a study with instruments in a certain time in the form of numbers or quantitative data with statistical tools to facilitate researchers in performing interpretation, using google Forms that help researchers to reach respondents quickly and with a wide range.

Variable		Indicator
Digital Marketing	Digital marketing is the activity and marketing activity of creating, communicating, and communicating value to consumers by using internet-based media facilitated by digital technology, based on sales volume before and after using digital.	1. Accessibility 2. Interactivity 3. Entertainment 4. Credibility 5. Irritation 6. Informativeness
Product Variety	Product diversity is a whole collection of products and goods that a particular seller offers to the buyer.	1. Size 2. Brands 3. Price 4. Display 5. Product Availability
Product Quality	Product quality is the ability of a product in carrying out its functions	1. Product Form 2. Product features 3. Performance 4. Accuracy/suitability 5. Durability 6. Reliability 7. Style 8. Design
Buying Interest	Buying interest is the possibility of consumers to buy a brand and service (Kotler and Keller 2016)	1. Transactional Interests 2. Referential Interest 3. Preferential Interest 4. Explorative Interest

IV. FIGURES AND TABLES

4.1 Research and Discussion

Descriptive analysis

Descriptive analysis is used to calculate the frequency of demographic information collected with the survey, such as age, gender, and income / allowance. This allowed the authors to form a richer understanding of the interest in buying skincare on the tik-tok application. The Data collected in this study as many as 200 respondents and the results are presented in the sub-sections below:

Age Discription

This description is to explain the age group of respondents collected by researchers in analyzing the answer data. The age group used consists of 3 age < 20 years, 21 years - 25 years, and > 25 years.

Age Group	Frequency	Percent
< 20 years old	34	17%
21 - 25 years old	131	65,5%
> 25 years old	35	17,5%
Total	200	100%

Source: Primary Processed Data, 2023

The description presented above shows that the majority of the samples in the study were aged 21 years - 25 years with 65.5%; followed by more than 25 years as much as 17.5%; and the remaining 17% were less than 20 years old.

Gender Discription

For this description describes the sex that exists in the sample of this study and the results are presented below:

Gender Frequency Discription Results		
Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	58	29%
Female	142	71%
Total	200	100%

Source: Primary Processed Data, 2023

The above results show that most of the sex in this study sample is female (71%) and the remaining 29% is male.

Income / Allowance Discription

For this description describes the income / allowance in this study sample and the results.

Results Discription Ferkuensi Income / Allowance		
Income Groups / Pocket Money (Rp.)	Frequency	Percent
< 1.000.000	65	32,5%
1.000.000 – 5.000.000	105	52,5%
> 5.000.000	30	15%
Total	200	100%

Source: Primary Processed Data, 2023

Based on the results of the above description shows that 52.5% of respondents have income / allowance of Rp. 1.000.000-Rp. 5.000,000; 32.5% income / allowance < Rp.1000,000 and the remaining 15% have income / allowance of more than Rp. 5.000.000.

A. Outer Model

The purpose of the outer model analysis is to ensure that the instruments in the variables have a level of validity and reliability that is concrete or not so that it can explain the variables of the research conducted. Below is the outer model produced, namely:

Source: Google form results quantitative method

1) Validity Analysis

Validity test is used to measure the validity or not of a questionnaire. This measurement is more of an indicator or question used to represent each research variable. In this study the validity test consists of *convergent validity* dan *discriminant validity*

Convergent Validity Validity is proven if obtaining scores on 2 instruments to measure the same or to measure a concept with different methods is highly correlated. Measurements in this test using *loading factor dan AVE (Average Variance Extracted)*.

Result Outer Loading			
Variabel	indicators	Outer Loading	Description
The influence of digital marketing (X ₁)	DM1	0.637	Valid
	DM2	0.730	Valid
	DM3	0.780	Valid
	DM4	0.682	Valid
	DM5	0.719	Valid
	DM6	0.719	Valid
	DM7	0.661	Valid
	DM8	0.670	Valid
	DM9	0.740	Valid
Influence Of Product Variety (X ₂)	RP1	0.722	Valid
	RP2	0.725	Valid
	RP3	0.723	Valid
	RP4	0.704	Valid
	RP5	0.668	Valid
	RP6	0.739	Valid
	RP7	0.688	Valid
	RP8	0.766	Valid
	RP9	0.753	Valid
Pengaruh Kualitas Produk (X ₃)	KP1	0.638	Valid
	KP2	0.787	Valid
	KP3	0.726	Valid
	KP4	0.803	Valid
	KP5	0.800	Valid
	KP6	0.734	Valid
	KP7	0.743	Valid
	KP8	0.703	Valid
Buying Interest (Y)	MB1	0.760	Valid
	MB2	0.825	Valid
	MB3	0.794	Valid

MB4	0.708	Valid
MB5	0.743	Valid
MB6	0.770	Valid
MB7	0.677	Valid
MB8	0.740	Valid

Source: Primary Processed Data, 2023

It can be seen that the loading factor test on each question is good for digital marketing variables, Product variety, product quality, and purchasing interest the resulting value > 0.6 then it can be stated that each question used is valid. The second test using the average Variance Extracted (AVE) is:

Result Average Variance Extracted (AVE)				
Variabel	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Description		
Digital Marketing (X1)	0.564	Valid		
Product Quality (X3)	0.553	Valid		
Variety Of Products (X2)	0.520	Valid		
interest to buy (Y)	0.568	Valid		

Source: Primary Processed Data, 2023

Based on the results of Ave analysis shows that the value of Ave in digital marketing, product variety, product quality, and buying interest > 0.5 then declared valid

Discriminant Validity

This test is done for evaluation of the reflection model using cross loading method.

Result Cross Loading				
Inquiry Items	Digital Marketing(X ₁)	Product Range (X ₂)	Product Quality (X ₃)	Buying Interest (Y)
DM1	0.637	0.510	0.510	0.476
DM2	0.730	0.560	0.553	0.574
DM3	0.780	0.564	0.629	0.646
DM4	0.682	0.494	0.556	0.558
DM5	0.719	0.552	0.603	0.568
DM6	0.719	0.615	0.568	0.538
DM7	0.361	0.306	0.350	0.278
DM8	0.670	0.542	0.511	0.495

DM9	0.740	0.547	0.533	0.544
RP1	0.625	0.592	0.722	0.561
RP2	0.613	0.530	0.725	0.599
RP3	0.505	0.577	0.723	0.513
RP4	0.537	0.544	0.704	0.502
RP5	0.503	0.482	0.668	0.495
RP6	0.546	0.563	0.739	0.534
RP7	0.601	0.655	0.688	0.556
RP8	0.607	0.581	0.766	0.597
RP9	0.589	0.590	0.753	0.556
KP1	0.496	0.638	0.557	0.562
KP2	0.616	0.787	0.606	0.600
KP3	0.500	0.726	0.563	0.489
KP4	0.587	0.803	0.579	0.540
KP5	0.641	0.800	0.642	0.564
KP6	0.594	0.734	0.594	0.571
KP7	0.600	0.743	0.604	0.582
KP8	0.538	0.703	0.533	0.550
MB1	0.568	0.515	0.552	0.760
MB2	0.671	0.621	0.655	0.825
MB3	0.660	0.645	0.589	0.794
MB4	0.545	0.561	0.522	0.708
MB5	0.548	0.575	0.531	0.743
MB6	0.624	0.598	0.583	0.770
MB7	0.511	0.509	0.593	0.677
MB8	0.532	0.493	0.541	0.740

Source: Primary Processed Data, 2023

This test is done by comparing the saru variables with other variables with the focus of observation on the variables studied. And proven results:

- **Variable Digital marketing (DM)** as an observation is seen compared to other variables (variety of products, product quality, and buying interest) the value of cross loading is greater than other variables so that it is declared valid.

- **Variable variety of products (RP)** as an observation is seen compared to other variables (digital marketing, product quality, and buying interest) the crossloading value is greater than other variables so that it is declared valid.

- **Product quality variables** as observations seen compared to other variables (variety of products, digital marketing, and buying interest) the value of cross loading is greater than other variables so that it is declared valid.
- **The variable of buying interest** as an observation is seen compared to other variables (variety of products, product quality, and buying interest) the cross loading value is greater than other variables so that it is declared valid.

2) Reliability Analysis

Analysis to measure the stability and consistency of an instrument in measuring a variable. The measurements used were composite reliability and cronbach's alpha.

Reliability Analysis		
Variable	Composite Reliability	Description
Digital Marketing (X1)	0.883	Reliabel
Product Quality (X3)	0.908	Reliabel
Ragam Produk (X2)	0.907	Reliabel
Buying Interest (Y)	0.913	Reliabel

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Description
Digital Marketing (X1)	0.849	Reliabel
Product Quality (X3)	0.883	Reliabel
Product Range (X2)	0.885	Reliabel
Buying Interest (Y)	0.890	Reliabel

Source: Primary Processed Data, 2023

Can be stated in this analysis using composite reliability and cronbach's alpha value > 0.7 good digital marketing variables, product quality, product variety, and buying interest then declared reliable

3) Analysis Of Classical Assumptions

In the classical assumption test used is a multicollinearity test which will test whether the regression model found a correlation between one or all independent variables.

Multicollinearity Analysis Results	
Variable	Buying Interest (Y)
Digital Marketing (X1)	3.178
Product Quality (X3)	3.127
Product Range (X2)	3.396

Source: Primary Processed Data, 2023

It can be said that the value of VIF in the relationship of good buying interest to digital marketing, product variety, product quality < 5 it can be said that there is no multicollinearity.

B. Inner Model

The Inner model focuses on the latent variable structure model where between these variables are assumed to have a linear relationship and have a causal relationship. Under the Inner model produced in the study, namely

Source: Google form results quantitative method

1) Goodness of Fit analysis

This analysis is to test whether the model used is feasible and has a model that is fit or not to the research conducted

a. Coefficient of Determination (R²)

To measure the variation of changes in the independent variable to the dependent variable. And this measurement is seen from the value of R square.

R Square Result		
Variabel	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Buying Interest (Y)	0.682	0.677

Source: Primary Processed Data, 2023

The resulting R square value of 0.682 (68.2%) shows that the digital marketing model, product variety, and product quality can measure the impact on purchasing interest by 68.2% and the remaining 31.8% are influenced by other independent variables outside the model studied.

2) Effect Size analysis (f²)

To assess the size of the effect between independent variables to dependent with Effect Size or f-square.

f square Result	
variable	Minat Beli (Y)
Digital Marketing (X1)	0.133
Product Quality (X3)	0.071
Product Range (X2)	0.062

Source: Primary Processed Data, 2023

The above results show that:

- The relationship of digital marketing to buying interest of 0.133 lies below between 0.02 – 0.15 then it can state a weak relation
- The relationship of product quality to purchasing interest of 0.071 lies below between 0.02 – 0.15 then it can state a weak relation
- The relationship of product variety to purchasing interest of 0.062 lies below between 0.02 – 0.15 then it can state a weak relation

3) Stone Geisser Analysis (Q2)

To build a model that measures how good or relevant an observation score is produced by the model and estimates its parameters. It is measured by Q square.

Q Square Result		
Variable	Q ²	Description
Buying Interest (Y)	0.378	Have value <i>predictive relevance</i>

Source: Primary Processed Data, 2023

Q square results show that $0.378 > 0$ can be interpreted that the model of product variety, product quality, and digital marketing is a relevant model in explaining the influence of buying interest.

4) Normed Fit Model (NFI) analysis

To measure whether the model produced in this study has a model that is fit or feasible in the test.

NFI Result		
	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.066	0.066
Chi-Square	1222.559	1222.559
NFI	0.720	0.720

Source: Primary Processed Data, 2023

The results that have been analyzed indicate that the NFI value of $0.720 > 0.1$ then it can be said that the resulting Model is a fit model.

5) Hypothesis Analysis

to see the T statistic and P Values where t aims to determine how much influence the independent variable to the dependent variable partially. In smart PLS seen from the path coefficient that shows the effect or influence of the independent variable to the dependent variable

Path Coefficient Result			
Model	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Digital Marketing (X1) - >Buying Interest (Y)	0.367	4.263	0.000
Product Quality (X3) - >Buying Interest (Y)	0.265	3.665	0.000
Product Range (X2) - >Buying Interest (Y)	0.260	2.783	0.006

Source: Primary Processed Data, 2023

Based on the results of analysis with the above model can be interpreted is:

It can be seen that in the analysis of digital marketing coefficient value 0.367 (positive) with a p value of 0.000 indicates that the value of $0.000 < 0.05$ means that digital marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchasing interest.

Analysis of product variety coefficient value of 0.260 (positive) with p value of 0.006 shows that the value of $0.006 < 0.05$ means that product variety has a positive and significant effect on purchasing interest.

Analysis of product quality coefficient value 0.3265 (positive) with p value 0.000 shows that the value of $0.000 < 0.05$ means that product quality has a positive and significant effect on purchasing interest.

4.2 Discussion

1. The importance of Digital Marketing and buying

The results found in this study indicate that digital marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchasing interest. This illustrates that the stronger the digital marketing, the interest generated will be stronger as well.

Digital marketing is the latest marketing tool commonly used for communication and promotion of services and products without limitation of time, location and cost (Kim & Ko, 2012). With digital marketing, consumers can more easily find information about a product. This can strengthen the consumer's purchase intention for the product. In addition, research in the city of Surabaya also mentions that digital marketing affects purchase intentions (Kaihatu, 2020). Proper digital marketing can easily arouse consumer buying intent towards a product.

2. The Relationship of Product Variety to Purchasing Interest

The results found in this study indicate that the variety of products has a positive and significant effect on purchasing interest. This illustrates that the more variety of products offered, the interest generated will be stronger as well.

Bhatnagar & Sham, (2014) argue that the more variety of products owned, the more likely it is to meet the needs of buyers, and buyers prefer online stores with a large variety of products. Because it can increase buyer satisfaction and purchase motivation Park & Kim, (2003). The more variety of products in a market, the more likely they are to buy back the product Alvian & Prabawani, (2020).

3. Relationship of product quality and buying interest

The results found in this study indicate that product quality has a positive and significant effect on purchasing interest. This illustrates that the better the quality of the product used, the interest generated will be stronger as well.

Kotler and Armstrong (2012: 283) stated that product quality is related to the expertise of a product in carrying out its functions, including the totality of products, reliability, accuracy, ease of operation and repair, and other valuable attributes. According to Gaol et.al (2016: 127) posits that product quality is the expertise of a product to fulfill its functions. Liao (2018) which shows the quality of the product, as well as the price influence on consumer buying interest. With the improvement of product quality and keep innovating, consumers can be interested in buying products in accordance with what they expect, so that product quality factors can affect consumer buying interest Annafik (2012) and Meiliani (2015)

V. CONCLUSION

A. Based on the results of research that has been done in Chapter 4, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Digital marketing variables have a significant positive effect on the interest in buying Skincare products on the TIKTOK application so that hypothesis 1 is accepted
2. Product variety variables have a significant positive effect on the interest in buying Skincare products on the TIKTOK application so that hypothesis 2 is accepted
3. Product quality variables have a significant positive effect on the interest in buying Skincare products on the TIKTOK application so that hypothesis 3 is accepted
4. Digital marketing models, product variety, and product quality only had an impact on purchasing interest of 68.2%.

B. Limitations of research

This study has limitations and is expected to be perfected in the next study.

The main limitation of this study is that this study only examined several independent variables, namely digital marketing & product variety, product quality and dependent variables, namely purchasing interest

C. Suggestions

1. For future research, there needs to be variables in the advanced model studied in order to be able to see the factors of interest in buying Skincare products on TIKTOK in 100%.
2. Due to the large reach of the TIKTOK application, it is necessary to add samples in the future so that the results can accurately read the phenomena that have been studied.
3. The company needs to do a more aggressive strategy again because the TIKTOK application has a great market opportunity in generating new prospective customers as evidenced by the results, both digital marketing, product variety, and product quality have a significant effect on buying interest.

REFERENCES

- [1] Alvian, M. S., & Prabawani, B. (2020). The effect of sales promotion and product diversity on shopee on repurchase interest through customer satisfaction as an intervening variable. *Journal of Business Administration (JAB)*, 9(1), 191-200.
- [2] Annafik, A. F. (2012). Analysis of the effect of product quality, price and attractiveness of advertising on interest in buying Yamaha motorcycles (Case Study on consumers Yamaha SS Kedungmundu Semarang Branch). (Thesis S-1). Semarang: Diponegoro University
- [3] Bhatnagar, A., & Sham, S. S. (2014). Allocating a hybrid retailer's assortment across retail stores: Bricks-and-mortar vs online. *Journal of Business Research*, 67(6), 1293-1302.
- [4] Desara, T., & Hidayat, T. (2021). Enrichment: Journal of Management is Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International License (CC BY-NC 4.0) Enrichment: Journal of Management enhances Repurchase intent in Retail: The Role of Customer Satisfaction, service. *Enrichment: Journal of Management*, 12(1), 325-329. 2021), 570(Icebsh), 888-892.
- [4] Gaol, N. T. L. (2016) " stress theory: Stimulus, response, and transactional, " *Psychology Bulletin*, 24(1), p. 1-11. doi: 10.22146/bpsi.11224.
- [5] Kaihatu, T. (2020). Purchase intent of fashion product as an impact of digital marketing, mediated by customer engagement in the generation Z. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 14(2), 61-66.
- [6] Kim, A. J., & Ko, E. (2012). Do social media marketing activities enhance customer equity? An empirical study of luxury fashion brands. *Journal of Business Research*, 65(10), 1480-1486.
- [7] Kotler, P and Keller. 2007. *Marketing Management (Volumes 1&2)*. Jakarta: PT. Index.
- [8] Kotler, P. & Keller, K.L. (2016). *Marketing Management (15th Ed)*. New Jersey: Pearson Education.
- [9] Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2012). *Marketing Management (14 Global)*. Pearson Prentice Hall.
- [10] Meiliani, N. and Ferdinand, A. T. (2015) ' analysis of the effect of Product Design attractiveness, promotional attractiveness, and quality perception on brand image and its impact on consumer purchasing interest (study on prospective Honda Beat Pop consumers at Nusantara Sakti Purwokerto dealers)', *Diponegoro Journal of Management*, 5(1), pp. 1-11.
- [11] Pangkey, F. M., Furkan, L. M., & Mulyono, L. E. H. (2019). The influence of Artificial Intelligence and Digital Marketing on consumer buying interests. *Jmm Unram - Master of Management Journal*, 8(3), 258-269.
- [12] Park, C. H., & Kim, Y. G. (2003). Identifying key factors affecting consumer purchase behavior in an online shopping context. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 31(1), 16-29.
- [13] Rainy, A., & Widayanto, W. (2020). The effect of product diversity and e-service quality on repurchase interest through Consumer Satisfaction (Study on Diponegoro University students of Zalora customers). *Journal Of Business Administration Science*, 9(1), 149-156.
- [14] Romadlon, A., Marlien, R. A., & Widyasari, S. (2020). The Effect Of Digital Marketing, Trust and Product Quality on Purchase Intention (Study on Kawaii Chocolate Instagram Account). *Proceedings Of The Senate*, 2016, 701-707.
- [15] Werry, F. A. (2020). The effect of DIGITAL marketing and product quality on purchasing decisions (Empirical Study on Sanata Dharma University students who bought Local Brand shoes on Online buying and selling applications and social Media). In *Sanatan Dharma University*, 3 (1).